

Genomic and Genetic studies of Systemic Sclerosis: a systematic review

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Abstract

Systemic Sclerosis is an autoimmune rheumatic disease characterised by fibrosis, vasculopathy and inflammation. The exact aetiology of SSc remains unknown but evidences show that various genetic factors may be involved. This review aimed to assess HLA alleles/non-HLA polymorphisms, microsatellites and chromosomal abnormalities that have thus far been associated with SSc. PubMed, Embase and Scopus databases were searched up to July 29, 2015 using a combination of search-terms. Articles retrieved were evaluated based on set exclusion and inclusion criteria. A total of 150 publications passed the filters. HLA and non-HLA studies showed that particular alleles in the *HLA-DRB1*, *HLA-DQB1*, *HLA-DQA1*, *HLA-DPB1* genes and variants in *STAT4*, *IRF5* and *CD247* are frequently associated with SSc. Non-HLA genes analysis was performed using the PANTHER and STRING₁₀ databases. PANTHER classification revealed that inflammation mediated by chemokine and cytokine, interleukin and integrin signalling pathways are among the common extracted pathways associated with SSc. STRING₁₀ analysis showed that *NFKB1*, *CSF3R*, *STAT4*, *IFNG*, *PRL* and *ILs* are the main “hubs” of interaction network of the non-HLA genes associated with SSc. This study gathers data of valid genetic factors associated with SSc and discusses the possible interactions of implicated molecules.

Keywords

Scleroderma; Systemic Sclerosis; Autoimmune Disease; Genetics; Systematic Review

1. Background

ACA, Anti-Centromere antibody; AID, Autoimmune Disease; ARA, Anti-RNA Polymerase III antibody; ATA, Anti-Topoisomerase I antibody; SSc, Systemic Sclerosis; dcSSc, diffused cutaneous SSc; lcSSc, limited cutaneous SSc; GWAS, Genome Wide Association Study; HLA, Human Leukocyte Antigen; MHC, Major Histocompatibility Complex; PAH, Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension; RA, Rheumatoid Arthritis; SLE, Systemic Lupus Erythematosus; VNTRs, Variable Number Tandem Repeats

Systemic sclerosis (SSc) refers to a systemic connective-tissue disease generally classified as an autoimmune rheumatic disease [1, 2]. It is characterised by excessive deposition of collagen in many tissues throughout the body, especially in the skin, causing hardening and thickening (fibrosis); vasculopathy; and inflammation associated with immune system abnormalities [1, 3]. SSc is a heterogeneous disease, as many organs of the body may be affected with variable manifestations among individuals and populations [4].

The disease is subdivided into limited cutaneous SSc (lcSSc) and diffused cutaneous SSc (dcSSc) based on clinical criteria. LcSSc tends to be less severe as skin thickening is limited to the upper neck, face and distal extremities [4, 5]. It is also known as CREST syndrome, due to the five common features; Calcinosis, Raynaud's phenomenon, Esophageal dysmotility, Sclerodactyly and Telangiectasias [4]. In contrast, dcSSc is more severe than lcSSc as internal organs (eg. heart, lung and kidney) are mainly affected and the condition progresses faster [4]. Internal organ complications include interstitial lung fibrosis, congestive heart failure, pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) and renal crisis [6-8]. Different types of autoantibodies are associated with each subgroup [9]. The presence of anti-centromere antibody (ACA) is mainly associated with lcSSc, whereas anti-RNA-polymerase family (anti-RNAP) and anti-topoisomerase antibody (ATA) (anti-Scl-70) autoantibodies are associated with dcSSc [10].

SSc does not occur randomly in the populations and is more common in women than men with a ratio of 3:1 to 6:1, according to the geographical region [11, 12]. Up to date, there is no clear aetiology for SSc, however evidences reveal that genetic factors may play an important role in triggering the disease [5]. Many Major Histocompatibility Complex (MHC)¹ and non-MHC genetic variations have thus far been associated with predisposition to disease [13]. Identification of the genetic variants based on the SSc heritability promises the discovery of genetic biomarkers. Genetic biomarkers can be defined as characteristics of DNA, RNA and protein that indicate normal/pathological processes and response to therapeutic interventions [14-16]. Therefore, genetic

¹ The MHC; also known as Human Leukocyte Antigen (HLA) in human is a set of genes located on the short arm (p) of chromosome 6 at position 21.3.

biomarkers are candidates for better classification, prognosis, diagnosis and therapeutic response of the disease.

During the recent years, several narrative and systematic reviews were published on SSc. Narrative reviews give a general background of the disease and discuss several topics e.g. genetics and epigenetics, therapies, biomarkers, pathogenesis and clinical manifestations of SSc without a structured methodological plan [9, 17-19]. On the other hand, systematic reviews are carried out using a specific methodological approach, thus all the relevant studies are included in the review and bias is minimised. Up to date, a small number of systematic reviews were performed on SSc, eg. mortality and survival in SSc and proteomic biomarkers of SSc [15, 20]. Although, a number of genetic variants and abnormalities have been identified through genetic and genomic studies, and the most common variants/abnormalities have been mentioned in narrative reviews, to our knowledge, this is the first systematic review of the literature that explores these variations and abnormalities. This systematic review, aims at the assessment and comparison of HLA and non-HLA polymorphisms, microsatellites and chromosomal abnormalities associated with SSc thus facilitating a more accurate diagnosis, prognosis and therapeutic targeting.

2.1. Literature Search Methodology

To complete this review, three electronic databases were used. PubMed (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/>), Embase (<https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/embase-biomedical-research>) and Scopus (<http://www.scopus.com/>) databases were searched for all peer-reviewed articles. Searching was performed on 29th of July 2015 in PubMed (1965 -29th of July 2015), Embase (1947- 29th of July 2015) and Scopus (1976-29th of July 2015), using the following combination of search-terms: (“systemic sclerosis” OR “scleroderma” OR “systemic sclerosis” [MeSH] OR “scleroderma” [MeSH]) AND (“genomics” OR “genome” OR “genetic” OR “chromosome” OR “mutation” OR “polymorphism” OR “SNP” OR “genomics” [MeSH] OR “genome” [MeSH] OR “genetic” [MeSH] OR “chromosome” [MeSH] OR “mutation” [MeSH] OR “polymorphism” [MeSH] OR “SNP” [MeSH]). Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) were not used in Embase and Scopus databases, as they do not explode MeSH. Retrieved articles were imported in EndNote version X5 and duplicates were removed. Reviews, case reports, letters, author replies, news, editorials, conference abstracts, erratums, book chapters, notes, short surveys, conference reviews, invited articles, reports and posters were excluded (Supplementary Figure 1). Articles not written in the English language were also excluded. The remaining articles were manually assessed by screening title and abstract, and only case-control studies involving human participants, directly referring to SSc and genetics, with statistically significant data were included for full-text evaluation. Articles without an abstract and full-text were excluded. Full-text papers were further assessed for their eligibility. Studies have been included only if they provide sufficient details about the number of patients, number of controls, type of controls, ethnicity and p-values. Chromosomal and family studies were not assessed for their eligibility. Additional publications were selected manually by searching the reference list of recent reviews associated with SSc [5, 21-23]. This work was carried out by three independent reviewers, using the PRISMA guidelines [24].

2.2. HLA Nomenclature

HLA genes and alleles were reported with the current HLA nomenclature system following the principles established by the Nomenclature Update 2010 [25].

2.3. Genes Classification and Analysis

PANTHER

Non-HLA genes extracted from the reviewed studies were classified, using the Protein Analysis Through Evolutionary Relationships (PANTHER) – Gene List Analysis tool (pantherdb.org/) [26]. This tool was used to classify genes (and their proteins) into different groups/pathways.

STRING₁₀

The Search Tool for Retrieval of Interacting Genes/Proteins (STRING₁₀) (<http://string-db.org/>) [27] was used to assess the interactions of non-HLA genes extracted from the reviewed studies. The confidence level was set to 0.700 (high). Interactions were extracted based on co-expression, experiments and databases.

3.1. Search Outcome

Database searches resulted in 6933 records, 3575 of them duplicates. After duplicate removal, 1884 records were also removed as they were reviews (1041), case reports (144), letters & author replies (124), news (2), editorials (65), conference abstracts (422), errattums (9), book chapters (10), notes (24), short surveys (31), conference reviews (10), invited articles (1) and posters (1). The 1474 remaining articles were screened by title and/or by abstract; 1310 articles were excluded as they fulfilled the exclusion criteria and 164 full-text papers were further assessed for their eligibility. Inclusion criteria were fulfilled by 131 papers and these were used for this review. Nineteen papers were added after manual searching through the reference list of recent reviews on SSc. The 150 papers were summarised and relevant information (country, ethnicity, number/type of participants, variations/alleles, p-value, risk/protection etc.) is documented in Supplementary Tables 1-4b. For GWAS, HLA and non-HLA studies, only statistically associated variants/alleles ($p < 0.05$) were included in the tables. The entire process, the search results and the inclusion/exclusion criteria are shown in Supplementary Figure 1. These studies identified and/or investigated approximately 360 variants/alleles and 20 microsatellite markers in about 150 genes.

3.2. Family and Chromosomal Studies

Initial genetic association reports were based on chromosomal and family studies (Table 1; Supplementary Table 1). Most of these studies were published before year 2000, prior to the development of high throughput technologies. Eight family [28-35] and two chromosomal studies [36, 37] are included in this review. Family studies were performed on lymphocytes, leukocytes, peripheral blood mononuclear cells and DNA samples. These studies showed that chromosomal breakage (eg. ~ 3 kb loss of telomeric DNA repeat), changes in variable number tandem repeats (VNTRs), maternal microchimerism and an HLA class II haplotype are associated with a risk of developing SSc. Emerit *et al.* (1976) [28] showed that the rate of chromosomal breakages is not only increased in SSc patients, but also in their first degree relatives. Similar findings were highlighted by Rittner *et al.* (1988) [29], and they also suggested that this feature is mainly observed in combination with the *A1, Cw7, B8, C4AQOB1, DR3* HLA haplotype which is common in autoimmune diseases (AIDs). This finding

was supported by Artlett *et al.* (1997) [33] who noticed that a high number of SSc patients have compatible HLA class II haplotypes with their mother or offspring, compared to control individuals. In addition, Assassi *et al.* (2007) [35] showed that affected sibpairs have a high probability to share 1 or 2 HLA class II haplotypes. In previous studies, Artlett *et al.* (1996) [31, 32] used lymphocytes to demonstrate that Scleroderma patients and their relatives lost ~3 kb of telomeric DNA repeat and had variable number tandem repeats (VNTRs) allele alterations.

Chromosomal studies were performed on lymphocytes from patients/controls and reported that chromosomal breakage is associated with scleroderma and dcSSc susceptibility. Wolff *et al.* (1991) [36] used peripheral blood lymphocytes to show that Scleroderma patients have elevated rates of spontaneous and clastogen induced chromosomal damage compared to healthy controls. Casalone *et al.* (1995) [37] used cultured lymphocytes of subjects between 30 to 70 years old and reported that dcSSc female patients have a higher tendency to develop chromosomal abnormalities including +X, PCD(X) and chromosome breaks, compared to healthy controls. None of these studies presents a correlation between chromosomal abnormalities and the presence of autoantibodies or clinical symptoms in SSc. Furthermore, in a recent review carried out by Bossini-Castillo *et al.* (2015) [22] it has been reported that twin studies revealed low levels of SSc heritability.

3.3. GWAS studies

Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) examine common genetic variants/polymorphisms in different populations under case-control design to extract possible associations with a specific phenotype. GWAS are often followed by GWAS-follow up studies in order to further analyse the region where associations are observed. GWAS follow-up studies focus on associations with or without statistical significance that might be related with the disease [38].

Five GWAS [39-43], three GWAS follow-up [38, 44, 45] and one pan-meta GWAS [46] have been performed on SSc that included both HLA (eg. *HLA-DPB1/B2*) and non-HLA genes (including genes located in the HLA-region). The first GWAS was published in 2003 by Zhou. *et al.* [42] and identified microsatellite polymorphic markers that are associated with susceptibility to SSc (Table 2). These genetic markers are generally more informative than bi-allelic SNPs [47]. Zhou *et al.* (2003) [42] identified

an association of SSc with one HLA (D6S422) and sixteen non-HLA (D1S255, D1S206, D1S2800, D5S410, D6S264, D7S510, D7S661, D8S514, D14S63, D15S978, D19S221, D19S220, D20S107, D22S423, DXS1068, DXS8055) marker loci, some of them located within the same gene locus. These marker loci did not overlap with any of those identified in candidate gene studies. Thirteen haplotypes were also reported to present significant frequency differences between patients and healthy controls (Table 2; Supplementary Tables 2a and 2b). At loci 1q42.3, 6q23-27, and 6p22.3, two haplotypes with small allele size differences were significantly associated with SSc. The authors suggest that these haplotypes might have arose by new mutations at microsatellite loci on the ancestral haplotypes [42].

The rest of the GWAS were published after year 2009 [39-41, 43] and revealed HLA-allele and non-HLA SNP associations in a variety of genes (eg. *GRB10*, *PSORS1C1*, *STAT4*) with different functions. Ten HLA and 90 non-HLA SNPs have been associated with SSc subgroups (Supplementary Tables 2a and 2b). SNP rs1029541 at 7q21.11 (~17Kbp from *SEMA3A*) [39, 44], rs10488631 at 7q32-7q32.2 (*TNPO3-IRF5*) [39, 41, 45], rs2056626 at 1q24.2 (*CD247*) [39, 41, 45], rs310746 at 3p25 (*PPARG*) [39, 44], rs3821236 at 2q32.2-q32.3 (*STAT4*) [39, 41], rs6457617 at 6p21.3 (*HLA-DQB1*) [39, 40] and rs9855622 at 3p25 (*PPARG-TSEN2*) [39, 44] have been associated with SSc in more than one GWAS/GWAS follow-up study. SNPs within the *SEMA3A* gene have also been associated with SSc in two GWAS/GWAS follow-up studies; however different SNPs in each case [39, 44].

Despite the fact that the rest of the SNPs/genes were associated with SSc only once, the majority of statistically significant SNPs ($p < 0.05$) were re-examined in a replication study. Replication is an essential and useful tool for genotype–phenotype associations, as it evaluates significant findings from previous studies and provides credibility that initial findings were “true-positive” [48]. The three GWAS follow-up studies [38, 44, 45] focus on the analysis of selected SNPs from previous GWAS [39, 41], that either reach or do not reach genome wide significance in the initial GWAS.

In GWAS/GWAS follow-up studies some SNPs were associated with susceptibility to SSc, whereas in replication studies the same SNPs were associated with protection to SSc. This phenomenon is observed in genetic association studies and might be caused by bias or genuine heterogeneity. Bias in genetic association studies may be

introduced by a number of factors such as inappropriate study design, inappropriate selection of participants, genotypic and phenotypic errors and errors in statistical analysis [49]. In addition, genuine heterogeneity may decrease the estimation of risk for a specific genetic variation and reduce the statistical power of genetic association detection [50]. Therefore, genetic variations associated with SSc should be confirmed in replication and in large scale population studies [51]. For example, SNP rs3128965 in GWAS was associated with susceptibility to ATA+; whereas in a replication study it was associated with protection to ATA+ [43]. Some previous associations were not supported by the replication studies; thus it was difficult to assess their credibility (Supplementary Tables 2a and 2b). Replication of the initial associations in different populations and designs, supports the initial findings and a group of studies on the same association provides more accurate results and stronger evidences [52]. Lack of association in the replication phase could be due to the lack of statistical power, stratification of populations caused by the combination of individuals from heterogeneous genetic backgrounds, Type I errors and selection or publication bias [48].

Nine non-HLA SNPs (rs7574865, rs10168266 and rs3821236 in *STAT4*; rs2233287 and rs4958881 in *TNIP1*, rs4728142, rs12531711 and rs10488631 in *TNPO3/IRF5* and rs1378942 in *CSK*) and two HLA alleles (*HLA-DPB1*09:01* and *DPB1*13:01*) were also identified in candidate gene studies. SNP rs3821236 and *HLA-DPB1*13:01* allele were identified in more than one candidate gene studies. The most significantly associated SNPs (rs987870 in *HLA-DPA1/B1*; rs3128930 in *HLA-DPB1/B2*) were not identified in candidate gene studies. Many genes associated through GWAS/GWAS follow-up studies overlapped with those identified through candidate gene studies; however, the majority of SNPs associated through GWAS/GWAS follow up studies did not overlap with those identified through candidate gene studies. Some genes and/or loci contain many associated variants with different p-values; in *HLA-DPB1* the p-value of allele **03:01:01* is 0.021, whereas of **13:01* is 4.05E-12. Furthermore, some GWAS/GWAS follow-up studies extracted association with combinations of SNPs, some of them being protective and other susceptible to SSc [40].

3.4. HLA studies

Thirty-three out of the 150 reviewed studies describe case-control based association of HLA genes with SSc [53-85]. Most of these were published after year 2000 and focused on Caucasian populations. Twelve different genes (*HLA-B*, *HLA-C*, *HLA-DRA*, *HLA-DRB1*, *HLA-DRB5*, *HLA-DQA1*, *HLA-DQB1*, *HLA-DMB*, *HLA-DOA*, *HLA-DPA1*, *HLA-DPB1* and *HLA-DPB2*) located within the HLA-region (6p21.3) are reported to be associated with the development of SSc (Figure 1a). Two of the genes belong to HLA-Class I and ten to HLA-Class II. None of the genes belongs to HLA-Class III. Class II genes are more frequently associated with SSc compared to those in Class I. *HLA-DPB1*, *HLA-DQA1*, *HLA-DQB1* and *HLA-DRB1* genes of Class II are associated with SSc in more than five studies. On the other hand, *HLA-C* and *HLA-DMB* genes of Class I and Class II, respectively, are referred only in one study.

HLA genes/alleles/haplotypes have been associated with SSc subtypes, different SSc clinical characteristics and the production of autoantibodies. Although, HLA studies demonstrate various alleles and haplotypes which may play an important role in the susceptibility to SSc, they also showed several HLA alleles/haplotypes that are referred to as SSc protective (Supplementary Tables 3a and 3b). Kuwana *et al.* (1995) [62] reported that *DPB1*04:02* is associated with susceptibility to SSc (ACA+), whereas *DQB1*03:01* and *DQB1*03:03* are associated with protection to SSc (ACA+). In a more recent study, Rodriguez-Reyna *et al.* (2015) [83] show that *DRB1*11:04* is associated with susceptibility to SSc, whereas *DQB1*03:01* is associated with protection to SSc. It is also noted that different alleles within the same gene are associated with different SSc subgroups. Fanning *et al.* (1998) [66] report that ACA-positive patients are associated with *DQB1*05* whereas patients with ARA I/II/III antibodies are associated with *DQB1*02:01*. He *et al.* (2014) [82] observed that the *DRB1*03:01* allele is associated with susceptibility to SSc; whereas *DRB1*04:06* is associated with protection to SSc (Supplementary Tables 3a and 3b). Furthermore, studies which included more than one population demonstrate that the same genes and alleles (eg. *DRB1*11:04*) may have different association and statistical significance (p-value) among different populations [59, 60, 68, 71, 73, 74, 76]. None of these alleles and haplotypes were supported by a replication study (Supplementary Tables 3a and 3b).

The HLA region is highly variable and characterised by variations and polymorphisms that are associated with diseases [86, 87]. Several studies performed over the last years demonstrated that a series of human diseases, especially AIDs are more frequent in individuals that carry specific HLA-alleles [88-90]. Kapitany *et al.* (2005) [91] showed that susceptibility to Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is significantly associated with *DRB1*04:05* and *DRB1*04:08* in the Hungarian population. Shimane *et al.* (2013) [92] reported that Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) susceptibility is particularly associated with *DRB1*15:01*, *DRB1*09:01*, *DRB1*08:02* and *DRB1*04:01* in the Japanese population. Through this systematic review we may suggest that susceptibility to SSc is mainly associated with HLA-Class II instead of HLA-Class I or Class III alleles. Particularly *HLA-DRB1*, *HLA-DQA1*, *HLA-DQB1* and *HLA-DPB1* alleles were more frequently observed among the populations in the reviewed studies. More precisely, the *HLA-DRB1*01*, *DRB1*01:01*, *DRB1*03:01*, *DRB1*04:01*, *DRB1*08:01*, *DRB1*11:01*, *DRB1*11:04*, *DRB1*13:01*; *DQA1*04:01*, *DQA1*05:01*, *DQA1*01:01*, *DQA1*02:01*; *DQB1*02:01*, *DQB1*02:02*, *DQB1*03:03*, *DQB1*04:02*, *DQB1*05:01*, *DQB1*06:02*, *DPB1*03:01* and *DPB1*13:01* alleles were strongly supported to have either a susceptibility or a protective association with SSc subgroups (referred to in more than one study). Although, the above alleles are strongly associated with SSc, only *DRB1*01*, *DRB1*11:04* and *DQB1*05:01* alleles, and SNP rs28857130 showed significant association in meta-analyses. Other studies showed that particular HLA-alleles that are associated with SSc are also associated with other AIDs; *HLA-DRB1*01:01* and *DRB1*04:01* are also associated with susceptibility to RA [9] and *HLA-DRB1*13:01* is also associated with protection to RA [93]. These findings suggest that specific HLA-alleles could provide susceptibility or protection to several diseases, especially AIDs. However, particular alleles and haplotypes in other HLA-Class I/II genes (*HLA-C*, *HLA-B*, *HLA-DRA*, *HLA-DRB1*, *HLA-DMB*, *HLA-DOA*, *HLA-DPA1*, *HLA-DPB2*) are also associated with susceptibility or protection to SSc.

3.5. Non-HLA studies

SSc being an autoimmune disease is associated with specific variants in HLA-genes, however many variants in non-HLA genes are also associated with SSc. One hundred non-HLA studies were reviewed and about 90 non-HLA genes associated with SSc were gathered (Figure 1b; Supplementary Tables 4a and 4b) [80, 85, 94-191]. Twenty-

five of these studies were supported by replication studies. Non-HLA genes associated with SSc have a variable function and chromosomal location, eg. *RHOB* at 2p24 [173] mediates apoptosis and *MECP2* at Xq28 [170] is involved in the DNA methylation process. Furthermore, eight of the non-HLA genes (*AIF*, *C4A*, *C4B*, *NOTCH4*, *TAP2*, *TAP1*, *TNF*, and *PSORS1C1*) are located within the HLA chromosomal location (6p21.3). Several genes such as, *HIF1A* [132] and *CYP2D6* [152] are reported to be associated with SSc only in one study; whereas other genes such as, *CTGF* [119, 133, 141] and *IRF5* [129, 143, 160, 165, 185] have more frequently been associated with SSc. In addition, some genes have more than one variant/polymorphism associated with SSc. In total, about 240 polymorphisms/variations in the promoter, exons and introns of genes and 20 haplotypes were investigated.

These studies report a number of SNPs and genotypes which are either predisposing or protective to SSc subgroups. Some non-HLA studies identified epistatic interactions between SNPs and highlighted that some interactions are protective while others are susceptible to SSc [124, 168]. Although, some studies revealed an initial association between a SNP and the disease, lack of association has been observed upon replication. This is because the disease is very heterogeneous depending on the ethnic group and each variation has different statistical significance among different ethnicities. Furthermore, some SNPs are associated only with ACA-positive SSc patients or dcSSc and not with all SSc patients (Supplementary Tables 4a and 4b). Studies of different populations showed that there exist different SNP associations with SSc among populations. Dieude *et al.* (2011) [146] showed that SNP rs763361 (T) in *CD226* which is significantly associated with SSc ($p=6.92E-4$) in Italian patients is not associated with SSc ($p=0.20$) in German patients. Genetic variations which exist between populations might be a result of natural selection based on geographic regions or the genetic drift [192, 193].

Variants in *STAT4*, *CD247* and *IRF5* genes were associated with SSc in the majority of reviewed studies. Several variants were also identified in *IRF* (*IRF5*, *IRF7*, and *IRF8*), and *IL* (*IL1A*, *IL1B*, *IL2*, *IL2RA*, *IL6*, *IL10*, *IL10RB*, *IL13*, *IL13RA2*, *IL21*) gene groups, and in genes (*CD6*, *CD19*, *CD22*, *CD58*, *CD226* and *CD247*) that encode the cluster of differentiation (CD) molecules. In addition, rs7574865 and rs3821236 in *STAT4*; rs4728142 in *IRF5*; and rs844648 in *TNFSF4* (*OX40L*) were reported as the most frequently associated SNPs. SNPs rs35677470 in *DNASE1L3*; rs12528892 in

TAP2; rs9494883, rs5029939 and rs7749323 in *TNFAIP3*; and rs7574865 in *STAT4* revealed the strongest associations with SSc. Strong association of rs35677470 with SSc subgroups was reported in two independent studies. However, the very strong associations initially displayed with SNPs rs9494883, rs12528892 and rs7749323 were not supported in a replication study, suggesting that an uncertain association may exist between these SNPs and SSc. Furthermore, SNP rs35677470 in *DNASE1L3*; rs10488631 in *IRF5*; rs2305743, rs436857, rs8109496 and rs11668601 in *IL12RB1* showed the strongest significant association in meta-analyses. Strong associations were reported for the rs1217414-rs2488458-rs2476602-rs12760457-rs2476601-rs2476600-rs3811021 combination of SNPs in *PTPN22* [121] and rs2239673-rs763737-rs7061789-rs1059702 in *IRAK1* [151]. Despite evidences that there is a lack of association of the R620W (1858C>T) polymorphism with SSc [194], Dieude *et al.* (2008) [121] in a subsequent study reported that the *PTPN22* haplotype carrying the 1858T allele or 1858C allele is associated with susceptibility or protection to SSc, respectively. Three GWAS [39, 41, 45] revealed an association of SNP rs2056626 (*CD247*) with susceptibility to SSc, whereas a more recent study of the Han Chinese population did not support this association [195]. Takeuchi *et al.* (2000) [95] and Susol *et al.* (2000) [96] highlighted that microsatellite markers in *TNFA*, *TGFB3*, *TGFB2* and *TIMP* are also associated with SSc subgroups (Table 2).

Many of the genes and SNPs currently associated with SSc, are also associated with other AIDs. SNP rs2476601 (*PTPN2*) which is associated with SSc is also associated with Type I Diabetes and RA [196, 197]. *PTPN2* is also associated with Crohn's disease through SNPs rs2542151 and rs2542152 [198]. *STAT4* rs7574865 associated with susceptibility to SSc, also confers susceptibility to RA [196]. Variations in *STAT4* have been associated with susceptibility to SLE and Sjogren's syndrome [199, 200]. Variations in the *IRF5* gene, which encodes a transcription factor that controls the activity of the immune system, are strongly associated with Multiple Sclerosis, SLE and SSc susceptibility [129, 201, 202]. In a recent review, Bossini-Castillo *et al.* (2015) [22] reported that an important portion of SSc risk factors overlap with risk factors of RA and SLE. These findings indicate that these genes and variants might play an important role in the regulation of AIDs mechanisms/pathways; therefore do not affect only a particular disease but a group of AIDs.

3.6. ImmunoChip based studies

ImmunoChip is a custom SNP genotyping array (Illumina Infinium platform based) that contains probes for approximately 200,000 variations across approximately 200 autoimmunity related loci. It is mainly used for fine mapping of GWAS significant loci and for deep replication of meta-GWAS in AIDs, including SSc [203, 204]. Mayes *et al.* (2014) recently reported a comprehensive analysis of associations between SSc subtypes and the HLA region, performed on a large number of cases and controls of European ancestry, using the ImmunoChip array [80]. A group of HLA and non-HLA SNPs as well as HLA alleles and amino acid residues were tested. Results showed that seven SNPs and six polymorphic amino acid positions in the HLA region are significantly associated with SSc and serological subtypes (ATA+/ACA+). Furthermore, an association of SSc with non-HLA *ATG5* and *DNASE1L3* genes, as well as the *SCHIP1-IL12A* locus and *TREH-DDX6* loci were reported [80]. In addition, ImmunoChip analysis in Australian SSc patients revealed association of SSc with eight loci, five of them (*VCAM1*, *TNP03-IRF5*, *STAT4*, *DNASE1L3* and *HLA-DRB1*) significantly associated through a replication study, as well [85].

3.7. Genes Classification and Analysis

The relation between the SSc associated non-HLA genes remains to be unravelled. Some of these genes may be interconnected through the same pathway. Therefore, non-HLA genes associated with SSc through both GWAS and candidate gene studies have been classified using the PANTHER-Gene List Analysis tool. Results confirm the heterogeneity of SSc as these genes are implicated in 37 different pathways. Some of these genes are involved in common pathways, but not all of them (Supplementary Figure 2). SSc pathogenesis is extremely complex and several biological processes (eg. inflammation and fibrosis), cell types (eg. immune cells, endothelial cells and fibroblasts) and molecules (eg. CTGF) are implicated [9]; therefore, all the PANTHER-analysis extracted pathways are related to the disease in different ways. In addition, some of the extracted pathways have been associated with other diseases such as Alzheimer and Parkinson. According to the PANTHER analysis results, inflammation mediated by chemokine and cytokine, interleukin, integrin, gonadotropin-releasing hormone receptor pathway, and Toll receptor signalling pathways are among the common extracted pathways. Several studies showed that the integrin signalling

pathway plays an important role in the response against the AIDs; as integrin molecules are expressed in many types of immune cells [205-208]. In addition, integrin is associated to fibrosis, a main pathology of SSc, through activation of the pro-fibrogenic TGF β 1 factor [209]. The interleukin signalling and inflammation mediated by chemokine and cytokine signalling pathways also play an important role in AIDs, as chemokine and cytokine molecules are proteins responsible for control of trafficking, responses and cellular arrangement of the immune system [210-212]. Interestingly, human chorionic gonadotropin is implicated in autoimmunity and is suggested as an immunoregulator of the abnormal cytokine release [213]. The Toll receptor signalling pathway is also essential for AIDs as Toll-like receptors recognise pathogen components, and are involved in the innate immune responses and the activation of the adaptive immune system [214, 215]. Wnt signalling is implicated in the pathogenesis of AIDs by affecting the immunosuppressive T regulatory cells [216]. Furthermore, the canonical Wnt signalling is hyperactivated in SSc skin biopsy and promotes fibrosis [217]. In addition, apoptosis, a primary event in SSc pathogenesis, is affected by a specific antibody through the Fas pathway [218].

The STRING₁₀ database was used to assess whether SSc associated non-HLA genes may have an interaction through their respective proteins. Only interactions that include direct and indirect association with high confidence score (0.700), and are derived from three active prediction methods; co-expression, experiments and databases were extracted (Supplementary Figure 3). Results indicate that although some genes illustrate high confidence score of protein–protein interaction networks (eg. *TNFAIP3-NFKB1*), approximately half of the genes do not show any evidence for protein-protein interaction (eg. *MIF*, *ATG5*, *TAP2*). *ESR1-PPARG* have a very high confidence score (0.991) of association based on all the three types of evidences; co-expression, experiments and databases. In contrast, *NOS3-ESR1* and *STAT4-NFKB* show lower confidence score of association based on two (0.955) and one (0.899) type of evidences, respectively. Several genes interact, because they are involved in the same group. For example, genes involved in ILs and IRFs groups are either directly or indirectly associated to each other. The genes that were identified to be involved in interleukin signalling pathway and chemokines and cytokine signalling pathway through the PANTHER databases, also show direct or indirect interaction to each other by the STRING₁₀ analysis. STRING₁₀ analysis clearly revealed that *NFKB1*, *CSF3R*,

STAT4, *IFNG*, *PRL* and *ILs* (eg. *IL10*, *IL13*, *IL6*, *IL2*, *IL1B*, *IL2RA*, *IL12RB2*) in particular stand out as the main “hubs” of interaction. The correlations between the “hub” genes and their interconnected genes are important parameters for the investigation of new interaction pathways, which may lead to developing new therapeutic approaches for the future.

3.8. Strengths and Limitations

The strength of this systematic review is that it includes a comprehensive search of published studies on variations, polymorphisms, mutations and chromosomal abnormalities associated with SSc. The sample size and statistical power are essential parameters for successful genetic association studies. In order to get a sufficient statistical power, the sample size should be calculated taking into consideration the number of variants and the type of the disease that will be studied. Several of the studies were carried out on a small number of participants (eg. 20 to 80), thereby over-estimating the magnitude of an association or increasing the probability of false-positive results [219]. This also causes low statistical power in the reproducibility of the results. In some cases the number of patients and controls was not equal, making the study less efficient. Many initially discovered associations have not been confirmed by replication studies and thus the credibility has not been improved [52]. Also different p-value models are presented among the studies, thus hindering comparison of the statistical significance. For a very small number of old studies, the access to full-text was not possible; thus some details and variants were not reviewed. The quality of the meta-analysis part could not be evaluated because the majority of papers did not provide sufficient details i.e. frequency of included SNPs in each individual study, heterogeneity, etc. Most papers did not carry out a formal meta-analysis but combined two or three populations to get a pooled OR. In these cases, the rules governing meta-analyses were not necessarily applied.

4. Conclusion

The results of this systematic review suggest that various genes and variants play a critical role in the pathogenesis of SSc. Family and chromosomal studies provided evidences that chromosomal breakage is a main feature in members of Scleroderma families. HLA-studies showed that alleles in *HLA-DRB1*, *HLA-DQA1*, *HLA-DQB1* and *HLA-DPB1* are more frequently associated with SSc as well as with AIDs. Non-HLA studies provided a large number of genes associated with SSc. Variations in the *STAT4*, *CD247* and *IRF5* genes are most frequently associated with SSc subgroups. SNPs rs35677470 in *DNASE1L3*; rs12528892 in *TAP2*; rs9494883, rs5029939 and rs7749323 in *TNFAIP3*; and rs7574865 in *STAT4* showed the strongest association with SSc subgroups. Use of large scale populations and study of new populations may enable the discovery of additional and stronger variants that are associated with SSc. Such variants will be useful for the development of new prevention, diagnosis and treatment targets. The inflammation mediated by chemokine and cytokine pathway, interleukin and integrin signalling pathways are also critical in the pathogenesis of SSc. *NFKB1*, *CSF3R*, *STAT4*, *IFNG*, *PRL* and *ILs* clearly stand out as the main “hubs” of non-HLA gene interaction networks. Therefore, they are essential for the investigation of new interaction pathways associated with SSc and for developing new aspects for future studies.

Author contributions

All authors contributed to literature search, screening and data extraction procedure. Paraskevi Chairta carried out the gene analysis procedure and drafted the manuscript. Kyroula Christodoulou and Paschalis Nicolaou revised and approved the final manuscript.

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Supplementary

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in Excel, Word, PDF and TIFF files.

Table 1

Description of Family and Chromosomal Studies associated with SSc subgroups.

Family Studies

A/A	Type of cells	Number of Participants	Type of mutation or association	More frequent	p-value	References
1		54 apparently healthy relatives of 29 scleroderma patients/40 HCs	increased chromosomal breakage	brothers and sisters of patients (86%), children of patients (68%)		[28]
2	lymphocytes	28 patients with scleroderma (SSc)-5 with CREST syndrome, 4 with incomplete CREST, 1 overlapping syndrome and 18 with progressive SSc-38 first-degree relatives in 9 families/16 unrelated HCs from Germany and the United Kingdom	an increased chromosomal breakage rate (ICBR)	in half of their first-degree relatives and in 27 of 28 patients with SSc		[29]
			ICBR trait showed close linkage with the HLA region (A1, Cw7, B8, C4AQOB1, DR3 haplotype) on chromosome 6	in the 6 informative of the 9 families		[29]
3	DNA extracted	58 probands with SSc, 218 first degree relatives and 22 spouses (44 families)	6/13 of ACA+ were either HLA-DR1 or HLA-DR4 positive			[30]

4	lymphocytes	43 SSc patients, 182 family members/96 age-matched HCs	3 kb loss of telomeric DNA repeat	SSc patients and family members		[32]
5	peripheral blood lymphocytes	49 scleroderma families/45 HC families	variable number tandem repeats (VNTRs) allelic alterations	probands 39.3%	p < 0.00001	[31]
				siblings 15.3%	p = 0.007	[31]
				offspring 21.7%	p = 0.0009	[31]
6	peripheral blood leukocytes	families 37 SSc patients/families of 42 HC individuals	Families of SSc patients had HLA class II haplotypes compatible with either their offspring or their mother	Families of SSc patients- 26/37 (70.2%)	p=0.00003	[33]
7	peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs)	26 SSc women/41 HC women	Increased frequency of MMc in PBMCs of SSc compared with HC	SSc women	p=0.001	[34]
8	DNA samples	710 SSc families/18 multicase families	1 or 2 HLA class II haplotype sharing between SSc sibpairs	SSc sibpairs	p = 0.011	[35]

Chromosomal Studies

A/A	Type of cells	Number of Participants	Chromosome abnormalities	More frequent	p-value	References
1	peripheral blood lymphocytes	10 patients with scleroderma/21 HCs	elevated rates of spontaneous chromosomal damage	Scleroderma patients	p = 0.002	[36]
			bleomycin induced chromosomal breakage	Scleroderma patients	p = 0.041	[36]
			streptonigrin induced chromosomal breakage	Scleroderma patients	p = 0.035	[36]
			4-nitroquinoline-1-oxide induced chromosomal breakage	Scleroderma patients	p=0.032	[36]
2	cytogenetically cultured lymphocytes	28 females with dcSSc/28 female HCs (30-70 yrs)	Triplo X cells	dcSSc		[37]
			+X	dcSSc 30-50 yrs		[37]
			PCD(X)	dcSSc 30-50 yrs		[37]
			-X cells	HC		[37]
			chromosome breaks	dcSSc		[37]

Table 2

HLA and non-HLA Microsatellite Markers associated with SSc subgroups.

A/A	Country, Ethnicity	Sample size cases/HCs	Microsatellite Markers	SSc Subgroup	p-value (Risk/Protective)	References
1	Japan-Germany, Japanese, German	104 SSc (54 Japanese and 50 German)/383 HC (69 Japanese and 314 German)	TNFa (a13 microsatellite) §	Japanese SSc vs German SSc	p=0.011 (Risk)	[95]
			TNFa (a13 microsatellite) §	Japanese SSc vs German HC	p<1.0 E-5 (Risk)	[95]
			TNFa (a13 microsatellite) §	Japanese SSc with a-Scl-70 vs German SSc with a-Scl-70	p=0.021 (Risk)	[95]
			TNFa (a13 microsatellite) §	Japanese SSc with a-Scl-70 vs Japanese HCs	p=0.028 (Risk)	[95]
			TNFa (a13 microsatellite) §	Japanese SSc with a-Scl-70 vs German HCs	p<1.0E-5 (Risk)	[95]
2	UK, UK Caucasian	191 patients/196 HCs	D1S419	lcSSc	p=0.02 (Risk)	[96]
			D1S419	SSc	p=0.02 (Risk)	[96]
			D14S277	SSc	p=0.02 (Risk)	[96]

			D14S277	lcSSc vs dcSSc	p=0.01 (Risk)-lcSSc	[96]
			D14S277	dcSSc vs HCs	p=0.001 (Risk)	[96]
			DXS426	male SSc vs male HCs	p=0.03 (Risk)	[96]
3	Indian, Chowtan Indian	20 SSc and 76 HCs	D1S206	SSc	p <0.0001 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D1S255	SSc	p=0.0068 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D1S2800	SSc	p=0.0012 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D5S410	SSc	p <0.0001 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D6S264	SSc	p=0.0176 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D6S422 ^{\$}	SSc	p=0.0368 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D7S510	SSc	p=0.0017 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D7S661	SSc	p=0.005 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D8S514	SSc	p=0.0015 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D14S63	SSc	p=0.0173 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D15S978	SSc	p=0.0189 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D19S220	SSc	p=0.0175 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D19S221	SSc	p=0.0016 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D20S107	SSc	p=0.0095 (Risk)	[42] ^G
			D22S423	SSc	p=0.0005 (Risk)	[42] ^G

	DXS1068	SSc	p=0.0026 (Risk)	[42] ^G
	DXS8055	SSc	p=0.0082 (Risk)	[42] ^G
	D1S255, chr1p32-31 (127, 230, 233, 97, 209 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0058	[42] ^G
	D1S206, chr1p21.2 (178, 217, 210, 292, 132 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0015	[42] ^G
	D1S2800, chr 1q42.3 (169, 265, 85, 212 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0000	[42] ^G
	D1S2800, chr1q42.3 (169, 267, 85, 208 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0037	[42] ^G
	D6S422 [§] , chr 6p22.3 (165, 292, 307 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0012	[42] ^G
	D6S422 [§] , chr 6p22.3 (171, 292, 305 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0392	[42] ^G
	D6S264, chr6q23-27 (141, 114, 172 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0001	[42] ^G
	D6S264, chr6q23-27 (143, 114, 174 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0003	[42] ^G
	D7S510, chr7p12-11 (188, 177, 95, 208, 245 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0093	[42] ^G
	D8S514, chr8q24.12 (272, 156, 222 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0393	[42] ^G

D19S221, chr19p13.2 (105, 200, 161, 85 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0003	[42] ^G
D22S423, chr22q13.1 (137, 83, 307, 146, 248 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0100	[42] ^G
DXS8055, chrXq21-23 (223, 316, 272 haplotype)	SSc	p=0.0010	[42] ^G

^G, found in GWAS/GWAS follow-up/pan-meta-GWAS; ^S, gene is located in HLA region of chromosome 6

Figure 1: HLA (a) and non-HLA (b) genes associated with SSc over the number of studies in which they were detected. These were classified according to the type of study (GWAS-red colour, Immunochip-green colour and Independent HLA/non-HLA study-blue colour). Less common genes represent those genes that have been associated with SSc only once.

Supplementary Figure 1: Flow diagram summarising the search results from the electronic databases and exclusion/inclusion criteria.

Supplementary Figure 2: Bar Chart shows the pathways associated with the reviewed non-HLA genes.

Supplementary Figure 3: STRING₁₀ analysis of the non-HLA genes. The confidence level was set to 0.7 (high). Nodes represent proteins shown by gene names, and coloured lines represent the different types of evidence for the indicated association. Black, pink and blue coloured lines indicate co-expression, experiments and databases evidences, respectively. Light blue coloured lines indicate homology.

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